
COMMUNITY CENTRIC ASSESSMENT ON SUSTAINABILITY OF AFFORDABLE HOUSING PROJECTS IN SRI LANKA

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Abstract: Sri Lanka as a developing country has been experiencing a considerable housing shortage out of the population during last few decades. Although the country has adopted numerous approaches in establishing sustainable affordable housings, they are found being only short-term solutions. Therefore, the need of sustainable affordable housings has not effectively fulfilled yet specially within the urban high-density areas. The present study examines end-user's perspectives of sustainability in the government funded high-rise affordable houses in urban high-density areas. The study has adopted a qualitative research methodology while referring the sample to high-rise affordable housing projects of low and middle-income households at urban high-density areas in Sri Lanka. The primary data collection was subjected to the evaluation of case studies at Ratmalana, Kottawa, Pannipitiya, Wellawatta and Maradana in Colombo and interviewing low and middle-income households, experts of authorities, construction professionals and other related personals. The scope of the secondary data was ranged over the publications of authorities, books, journals, regulatory publications, newspapers and related other sources. The means of 'sustainability' is measured in terms of environmental and social parameters while analysis of the data is achieved by a content analysis. The findings of the research have revealed a gap in between adoption of sustainable principles during pre-construction phase and achieving the proposed sustainable performance by the end users. Hence, the study stresses the necessity of addressing changes in environment, population, economy, social formations and desires of end-users during the pre-construction phase.

Keywords: Affordable Housing, Sustainability, Post Construction, Sri Lanka.

1 Introduction

Housing is an essential, basic human need as it displays the standards, ambitions, desires and socio-cultural attributes of households as a whole (Hamdi, 1990). Thus, developing countries are generally challenged on the future of its settlements, against the backdrop of addressing issues of inadequate housing, rapid urbanization and lack of infrastructures (du Plessis, 2002:1). Inadequate housing has been a major issue in third world countries and subsequently, Sri Lanka faces numerous socio-cultural and economic issues in unplanned urbanization, poverty and rapid growth of urban population (Samaratunga, T., 2013). This concept was further stressed by Nair (2005) who mentions that developing countries suffer the most among other nations to acquire proper housing conditions. Although this problem is associated with numerous causes, the Central Bank report in 2006 revealed that the housing shortage is mostly influenced by slums, shanties and informal settlements, which encroach on crown lands in the city. The application of sustainable construction models for affordable housing strains identification of major means. The interpretation by Nallathiga, R (2010) best defines 'affordable housing' as the houses that are accessible at a cost that can be achieved by a modest household with an average annual income; statistically, to median price that can be afforded by median household; and symbolically, to right housing options to right income groups. Similarly, the term 'sustainability' is defined as the use of natural resources in such an equilibrium condition that they do not reach decay, depletion, non-renewable point and handing down the next generations by developing them (Yilmaz and Bakış, 2015), while 'affordable housing' refers to any type of housing (market or non-market provided) that is rented or purchased at a cost that is not beyond the financial capacity of a household (Wiesel, I., et al., 2012). In relation to the major means of considerations, this research becomes significant in integrating sustainability and affordability during post construction phase of government funded high-rise affordable houses in Sri Lanka. While sustainability is traditionally measured through Economic, Environmental and Social performance of projects, often how these parameters perform from users' experiences in the post project phases is not quite clear. In this research, an attempt has been made to gather the evidence from the end users of a few selected communities who reside in government funded affordable housing premises to understand how the sustainability is experienced or sustainable considerations are providing the end-results at the post construction phases of projects.

2 Background of The Study

The development of affordable housing models has been a longstanding discourse among researchers all over the world. 'Housing affordability has become a frequent terminology on the nature of the housing struggle in many nations' (Hulchanski, 1995). While numerous studies have stressed the impact of not owning liveable housing by some of the population, Musterd, 2010 emphasized that lack of sufficient habitable housing has become a global problem. This is further stressed by Samaratunga (2013) who emphasizes on the similar circumstances of having inadequate housing, in the Sri Lankan context. Although the country has adopted various strategies to enhance affordable housing, Niriella (2010) stressed the matter of not having long term significant solutions to any of these attempts except temporary fixes. Consequently, the report published by the Censes and Population Department of Sri Lanka (2007) revealed a considerable housing shortage among population. Hence, the existing housing shortage exposes unsolved issues of affordable housing in Sri Lanka. The report published by Bruntland (1987) defined 'sustainability' as

'meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs' in order to achieve providing necessities to the people while protecting the ability for the future generations to meet similar needs. While this concept has been adopted by numerous nations to provide housing for communities, 'The National Housing Policy' (2014) indicated its ultimate goal as 'to ensure the right to live in an adequate, stable, qualitative, affordable, sustainable, environment friendly and secure house with services for creating a high living standard on the timely needs of the people'. Thus, Fernando (2002) emphasized that most urban under-served settlers have suffered severe deterioration due to the poor maintenance and management of the building structures and their infrastructure. The same author has further discovered the causes for being unable to manage their houses as poor awareness, social status, level of education, lack of willingness, incorrect attitudes and bad habits of the communities. The defined findings as well as similar studies have revealed solid waste management, drinking water supply system, lighting systems, community centers and parking lots as the areas that required much needful attention in Sri Lanka. Hence, the government as well as private stakeholders have considered high-rises as the most sustainable solutions for urban high-density areas. Consequently, sustainable housing has been designed mainly based on social, economic and environmental aspects.

In examining if sustainable principles impact affordability in the Sri Lankan context, several projects undertaken by the government reveal that general sustainable criteria are insufficient in improving the degree of affordability. The 68 story Altair building in Colombo city and the 'Sahasapura' high-rise low-income housing project that comprised 671 housing units over 14 floors are some of the greater projects where the sustainable principles have been applied in housing projects. Thus, these projects have caused several controversies in the country in achieving the goals of the 'affordable housing' category, under the adopted sustainability measures. Hence, it is significant to adhere to the three conditions of social acceptability, economic viability and being environmentally friendly, while serving the purpose of affordable housing. Therefore, the present study has focused on verifying if adoption of sustainable principles in housing is affordable to the target groups of communities. The measures of sustainability may comprise evaluation of culture, heritage and other values of the households.

In assessing the scholarly views on 'affordable housing' in Sri Lanka, though Udawattha and Halwatura (2017) defined it as the ability to purchase a particular item; the practical implementations exhibit a vast range of complications in achieving this interpretation. The study conducted by Niriella in 2010 stated a tendency of Sri Lankan affordable housing projects to be beneficial for wealthy households except the aimed population. Similar misapplications have been found during the last few decades in leading the country's affordable housing projects being affected by political influences and poverty rather than considering community development. The overall combination of factors such as existing housing shortage, unsolved issues of affordable housing, insufficient interpretations on affordable housing and poverty further stresses the need of defining 'affordability' in the Sri Lankan setting, in contrary to the traditional framework to enable providing solutions for the defined associated complications. Therefore, the present study engages in identifying interpretations and defining a baseline for housing affordability in Sri Lanka. Accordingly, this study aims at evaluating the gaps of adopting affordable housing in urban high-density areas while achieving sustainable necessities to proceed with model

development, as it benefits in resulting defining policy frameworks in the Sri Lankan context.

3 Problem Statement and Objectives of The Research

Sri Lanka, in being an under developing nation faces inadequate housing problems in relation to the growth of population. Although numerous approaches were undertaken to overcome housing problems in urban high-density areas by the government and private sector of the country, the overall factors tend not sustaining the future needs due to lack of holistic planning. The present study examines way forward by reviewing and evaluating the possible sustainable solutions while interpreting affordability and sustainability on affordable housing in Sri Lanka.

The key objectives of the research include the following:

- I. To demonstrate the degree of living standards of affordable housings in urban high- density areas in Sri Lanka.
- II. To examine application of sustainable principles for affordable housings in urban high- density areas in Sri Lanka.
- III. To define Sri Lankan affordable housings in urban high-density areas in terms of sustainable solutions.

4 Research Methodology and Data Collection

The research methodology contains the research design that was adopted to realize the targets, objectives and questions of the study. "Research in modest expressions denotes pursuit for knowledge and a scientific and systematic exploration for evidence on a specific theme or subject, research methodology is a systematic approach that a research adopts to accomplish the research aims" (Creswell, 2009). The present study has adopted a qualitative approach to evaluate the aim and objectives of the research. The population of this study refers the affordable housing projects in Sri Lanka while the sample the is limited to high-rise affordable housing projects of low and middle-income households at urban high-density areas in Sri Lanka. The research has gathered primary data by evaluating 80 number of respondents at Ratmalana, Kottawa, Pannipitiya, Wellawatta, Maradana, in Colombo while interviewing middle-income households, experts of authorities, construction professionals and other related personals. These interviewees were sampled based on purposive sampling method. The purposive sampling technique which is known as judgment sampling, is the deliberate choice of a participant due to the qualities the participant possesses (Etikan, I., Musa, S.A and Alkassim, R.S., 2016). The secondary data was obtained via publications of authorities, books, journals, regulatory publications, newspapers and related other sources. The analysis of the data is designed to achieved by a content analysis with the use of attained results while focusing on cultural, heritage values and preservations that limit the housing sector in better planning for the community.

Figure 01: Location of the case study
Source: Google Map (Accessed on 29/07/2021)

The present study has evaluated the degree of sustainability of government funded high-rise affordable houses in Colombo by the means of environmental and social perspectives. According to the discoveries of Doloji, H (2018), addressing perspectives of communities is the core in infrastructure planning as social values denote the success or failure of such projects. In relation to the present study, the parameters of examining these aspects were concerned based on the environmental and social sustainability measures of GreenSL rating system issued by the Green Building Council, Sri Lanka. Consequently, the respondents were evaluated based on the following criteria.

Figure 02 GreenSL Rating System,
Source: Green Building Council, Sri Lanka.

5 STUDY FINDINGS

I. Environmental Sustainability of Affordable Housings in Urban High-Density Areas in Sri Lanka

Sri Lanka is divided into 9 provinces and each province is subdivided into several districts based on the geographical formation. Colombo in being one of districts in the Western province, ranges over 699 square kilometers. The department of census and statics (2020), Sri Lanka has estimated 77.6% of urban population in Colombo city. It has become Sri Lanka's most economic city since many years back. The analysis of both primary and secondary data has revealed the degree of application of sustainable principles in affordable high-rise housings in urban high-density areas in Sri Lanka. In assessing the impact of environment on living standards of building occupants, greater issues were found in increment of heat, obtaining fresh air, noise pollution, sanitary facilitations and green spaces.

Green Spaces and Green Materials

In examining the degree of heat experienced by the defined building users, 69.84% of them have experienced a greater heat during the day time and night time as well. The geographical formation of these residuals is evident that these residents are impacting by high-density population, global warming, lack of green spaces and design errors in major. One of response received by an interviewee emphasized that 2 × 2 ft² sized windows and lack of green spaces caused indoor heat gain during both day and night time. Colombo is the main commercial metropolitan city in Sri Lanka, with having the highest population and building density, making the city an ideal place to form Urban Heat Islands. (Dissanayake, at al 2020). The study findings of Census of Population and Housing (2012) have revealed that the highest number of household units have been recorded from the Western Province while Colombo containing residential population of 558755, making it the densest city in Sri Lanka. Apart from common impacts such as global warming and Sri Lanka being located near by the equator, these housings are having insufficient green spaces. Although most of these occupants were privileged by a common garden or an adjoining park in Colombo, the existing amounts of trees and plants are inadequate to overcome heat gain especially in high-rise buildings. In addition, the housing projects which were located close by Sri Lankan coastal line are experiencing a less heat as they get sufficient wind. Thus, the degree of existing green spaces is similar to the other building units. Additionally, the houses have initiated construction materials such as asbestos sheet for roofing, and excessive concrete structures while not adequately adopting sustainable building materials or energy efficiency sources.

Living Spaces

The proportion of population living in households is a factor of sustainability (Klopp, J.M. and Petretta, D.L., 2017). The present study has assessed end-user's perspectives on 'Design Factor' to demonstrate the degree of application of sustainable measures in government funded affordable high-rise projects, Colombo. Consequently, average dimensions and design principles of some of the case studies were identified as follows.

Average Values (Approximate)	Housing Projects in Ratmalana,	Housing Projects in Kottawa	Housing Projects in Pannipitiya	Housing Projects in Wellawatta	Housing Projects in Maradana
Number of bed rooms	02	02	02	02	02
Dimensions of room	130 ft ²	440 ft ²	693 ft ²	551 ft ²	622 ft ²
Dimension of kitchen	24 ft ²	36 ft ²	96 ft ²	36 ft ²	36 ft ²
Dimension of washroom	6ft ²	6 ft ²	8 ft ²	9.5 ft ²	8.5 ft ²
Number of members in a family	5	6	5	6	6
Dimensions of Living room and verandah	Majority had no living room or a verandah.	Majority had no living room or a verandah.	Living room: 924.9 ft ² Majority had no personal verandah.	Living room: 355 ft ² Majority had no personal verandah.	Living room: 412ft ² Majority had no personal verandah.

Table 01: Average values of living space dimensions

In global context, floor area per person is highly variable among countries, hence the median reported floor area per person is 14,4 sqm, with a global range from 2 to 69 sqm (Kozhenova, S., 2010). Thus, evaluation of the defined housing projects revealed that existing spaces are inadequate in relation to population growth. Limited living spaces also challenge achieving Green^{SL} criteria of indoor environmental quality.

Air Quality

The present study has exposed building users experiencing inadequate fresh air due to common factors such as excessive power generation, higher use of fossil fuels, emissions of motor vehicles, etc. In accordance with the According to the World Health Organization's guidelines (2020), the recommended maximum level of the annual mean concentration of PM2.5 is 10 µg/m³ and however, Sri Lanka has exceeded this as the most recent data reveals that the country's annual mean concentration of PM2.5 is 11 µg/m³. Additionally, the research has noted indoor air pollution within these affordable housings in Sri Lankan urban high-density areas. Consequently, the respondents are found consuming gas stoves, firewood, burning of waste, mosquito coils and cigarettes. Altogether both outdoor and indoor air pollution highly tends negatively impacting on good health of these building users in long term by causing diseases such as asthma, allergies, cancer, depression, heart strokes, etc. The World Health Organization has estimated number of deaths caused by indoor and outdoor air pollution in Sri Lanka to be around 4200 and 1000 deaths respectively. (Nandasena, S., Wickremasinghe, A.R. and Sathiakumar, N., 2012).

Noise Pollution

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines noise above 65 decibels (dB) as noise pollution. The housing projects being located in the most urbanized city in Sri Lanka has resulted its residents experience excessive noises throughout the day by traffic noise, night life, animals such as dog barks and even by the louder noises of televisions, radios of neighbors. The matter has also emphasized by Nagodawithana N.S., et al (2016). The residents at *Rathmalana* are even impacted by air traffic noise.

Sanitation

The affordable housing projects in Sri Lankan urban high-density areas have facilitated sanitary needs either attached to the residual units or as separate units. Although the residents who are accessible to attached washrooms are satisfied with existing sanitary facilities, the ones who consume common washrooms are found unsatisfied. According to them, school children are severely impacted as it takes more time to be in a que until they get the opportunity. Similarly, young women have undergone several infections such as UTI (Urinary Tract Infection) in consuming common washrooms. Thereby, secureness of environment sustainability becomes significant for affordable houses in Sri Lanka.

In overall, the defined housing projects are found not adequately fulfilling the sustainable criteria in preserving environmental perspectives during the pre-construction phase. The fishbone diagram stated below (figure no: 03) further illustrates potential causes and relative effect respectively. Accordingly, the state of environmental sustainability of the case study is revealed inadequate due to lack of green spaces and green materials, insufficient living spaces, poor indoor air quality, insufficient living spaces, noise pollution and inadequate sanitation.

Figure 03: Fishbone diagram for challenges of environment sustainability

II. Social Sustainability of Affordable Housings in Urban High-Density Areas in Sri Lanka

The 'New' Culture and Social Formation

The social formation of majority of the residents at most of the affordable housings in Colombo urban high-density areas were belonging to a specific social class. A huge population of Sahaspura belong to the lower or working class while majority of the Millennium City and Mattegoda are middle class (Niriella, N.C.,2012). As per the research discoveries, defined communities are found comprising of various types of residents at their schemes. Thus, the study has also revealed an emergence of a change in the existing culture due to the impacts of globalization, drug addiction, poverty, prostitution, depression, isolation, inequity and lack of education.

“When we were at slums, we had a unique way of living. But, the new community is a ‘Fruit-Salad’. We have residents form various professions and versions. New houses are environmentally better than earlier ones but socially we are unsecure. And we work hard to protect our children from negativities”

The residents' point of view on their social formation referred to a 'fruit-salad'. Similarly, together with other respondents' reviews, the study has exposed a change in the existing social formation within these housing units. This study becomes more significant as a majority of these changes were found influenced by similar communities lived in similar other housing units in Colombo. The cultural changes are also emerged creating a 'new culture' and accelerating social formation into an extent which contains inadequate sustainable attributes such as cultural dominance, lack of community engagement, inequity, social illness, etc.

Social Wellness

In assessing social wellness, the research has identified an increment in prostitution and consumption of drugs. Since most of the parents were engaged in prostitution, their children tended addicting into drugs. These have consequently accelerated smuggling and organized crimes in order to fulfill financial needs in reaching into drugs and prostitution. Similarly, the obtained data has disclosed most of the housing communities being dominated by an existing set of residents. These groups are found influencing on common opinions, decision makings and even the culture of the communities. Following responses are evident that they have undergone a change in their social formation during the past years.

*“There is a set of residents living here originated by ‘Thara-waththa’ and they domain here. Their children have the opportunity to attend reputed schools but they do a lot of party with loud noises. It’s difficult to concentrate on studies by then”. (*watta referes to a cluster of slums).*

Moreover, the respondents revealed difficulties in attaining a sufficient income in relation to the amount of basic expenses they bear.

Equity

Although initiation of these projects aimed at attaining new employment, education and social opportunities to the end users, practical implementation exhibits limited moments. Niriella (2012) exposed circumstances where poor community being treated minimum as the middle and the higher middle-income groups were benefited by various housing policies and housing programs. In relation to the discoveries of 'changes of social formation' by the present study, the existing low and low-middle income communities are found being influenced by such privileged middle and the higher middle-income sets in all above stated ways. A majority of the respondents aged between 11-29 years old exposed that they experience minimum opportunities at schools and interviewing for white-collar jobs as they have been labeled as inferiors. Although the ones who were originated from slums and socialized at new locations while undergoing several socio-cultural and economic transitions during past years, they still used to be treated based on their origin by the society. In addition, media is found highly impacting on their social formation. One of respondents at Sahasrapura housing revealed that some of their residents are always subjected to be a part of drug dealing or murdering cases as it was emphasized by the media, although they are not guilty. Afterall, residents being isolated due to any reason limits community involvements and social sustainability as a result.

Isolation

The nature of new culture exhibits poor sustainable attributes while containing dangers. Accordingly, another portion of this community exhibit resisting these cultural changes to achieve secureness for their families. As a result, they are found being isolated purposively or sometimes even with no hesitation. While most of the families purposely separate themselves from being a part of new culture, the domaining culture isolates the rest unintentionally. For an example, parents attempt separating their children from others to protect from negativities such as drug addictions, prostitution, mental illnesses, etc. The resulted state of social affairs also challenges the community being socially sustained. Apart of being isolated by their own community, the research has discovered an extent where they have been indirectly isolated by the society in general. Most of the youngsters and mid agers exposed being unequally treated in achieving education and employment opportunities. Some have stressed the matter of iconizing them based on the fact of being orient from Watta.

In addition to the isolation caused by cultural matters, the residents are also revealed being proceeding through self-separation due to the design factors of houses as design factors have not adequately addressed the need of privacy for the end-users. Most of the responses received by interviewees emphasized that higher noises (Ex: noise of the television, talking loudly, etc) distracts their neighbors. Similarly, some of the washrooms were designed as they disclose to front direction of the house hence their residents revealed the necessity of adequate privacy. Accordingly, the present study has revealed poor living conditions due to the proposed design during the pre-construction phase.

In overall, an inadequate status of social sustainability is discovered among the low- and middle-income residents at affordable housings in Colombo urban high-density areas due to an isolation undergone either by themselves, society or design factors while facing its relative circumstances.

Figure 04: Fishbone diagram of social formation resulted by 'new culture'

6 Conclusion

The study has examined the status of environmental and social sustainability of high-rise affordable housings in urban high-density areas in Sri Lanka through the perspectives of end-users. Consequently, they have exposed an inadequate degree of sustaining environmental and social perspectives. In accordance with environmental sustainability, design factor is found being one of a major cause for the existing issues in indoor heat exposure, indoor air quality, sound insulation, sanitary facilitations, living spaces and green spaces. Hence, the study has revealed that achieving post-construction environmental sustainability performance is challengeable in compared to the degree of sustainable principles integration during pre-construction phase.

The assessment of social sustainability enclosed emergence of a change in the existing social formation due to major two causes. First, the community has undergone a change once they were established at government funded houses due to the impact of mixed-culture at the same housing scheme and other housing schemes as well. Although these residents had a unique way of living before transforming into the present residents, the new culture initiated getting influenced by globalization, drug addiction, poverty, prostitution and depression. Second, the defined community is discovered isolating either by their own or by society. Self-isolation has empowered as a majority of individuals intended protecting their relatives from addicting into drugs, smuggling, prostitution, depression, etc; while 'design factor' of these residents played a dominant role as well. The community has also isolated by the society for being originally from slums and iconized as people with low qualities. The present study has discovered emergence of a 'new culture' empowered by above stated causes. The attributes of new culture are revealed not adequately sustainable as it challenges equity, living conditions, health and

safety, wellness, community engagement and existing culture. Therefore, expected social sustainability is found not adequately experienced by the residents of these houses.

Overall, the study has revealed a gap between adopting sustainable principles during pre-construction phase and achieving the proposed sustainable performance by the end users. Hence, the study stresses the necessity of addressing changes in environment, population, economy, social formations and desires of end-users during the pre-construction phase. Integration of this fact in decision making and policy planning may enable the nation to reach sustainable goals effectively.

Figure 05: Research Findings and Resolution

7 Recommendations

The present study has examined reliability of achieving pre-construction sustainable needs in the perspective of end-users. The findings denoted a gap in between pre-construction aspirations of sustainable goals and degree of sustainable performance during the post-construction phase. As the gap was emerged due to the changes of environment, population, economy, social formations and desires of end-users; the study suggests addressing those changes in pre-construction phase. In there, empowering employee's knowledge and awareness on such variances is also similarly important for effective decision making.

Additionally, adoption of sustainable criteria and standards during pre-construction phases and enhancement of sustainable awareness among construction professionals is significant. In reference to the defined case study, the matter of adequate living spaces can be overcome by initiating a new infrastructure while expanding the existing house spaces by combining adjoining areas into it. In assessing the degree of social sustainability, the findings suggested addressing the defined change in existing social formation in order to mitigate the emergence of forecasted culture and its negative circumstances. Therefore, updating the investment strategies with aiming at long-term benefits, establishment of rules, policies and monitoring systems to equally treat the poor, middle- and higher-income holders, addressing socio-economic and cultural needs during the initial phases on construction, expansion of legal compliances and programs to overcome social issues of poverty, living conditions, wellbeing, health and safety, community engagement, etc., are suggested to be implemented in the future. More importantly, a specific change on social mindsets can be performed to create an equally treated society.

8 Limitations & Further Study Directions

The research has evaluated sustainable approaches of high-rise affordable housing projects for low and middle-income households in urban high-density areas in Sri Lanka. The collection of data was limited to the areas of Ratmalana, Kottawa-Pannipitiya, Wellawatta and Maradana in Colombo. Hence, it is proposed to undertake further studies into a wider range over the specified areas in Sri Lanka. Since the present study has focused on high-rise affordable houses, the scope can be expanded into individual residential units as well. Moreover, a separate study can be undertaken to evaluate the status of economic sustainability as the present research has assessed 'sustainability' in terms of social and environmental perspectives.

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